

1 **HLA-E and HLA-G are modulated during transition from pluripotency to the TE, but HLA-L is not.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of a
9 function for class I HLA-E and HLA-G receptors in lineage commitment. The data - conserved expression
10 between hES cells and the in vitro differentiated TE - suggested HLA-L marked primitive tissues. We
11 recently demonstrated evidence supporting a developmental function for MHC receptors MICA and MICB.

12 Citations

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